

Environmental awareness, attitudes, and practices: A case study of a selected private senior high school in Surigao City, Philippines

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Abstract

Humankind must respect and value the environment's delicate balance to safeguard and preserve it for the present and the future. During the academic year 2022-2023, this study set out to investigate the environmental practices, attitudes, and awareness at a particular private senior high school in Surigao City, Philippines. The Environmental Awareness, Attitudes, and Practices Questionnaires were used in this correlation quantitative study, which included SHS students from a selected private educational institution in the Philippines. The findings showed that the respondents' levels of environmental awareness are "very high", and the environmental practices are "very good". Using the Pearson correlation analysis, it was discovered between the two variables show significance and has a positive correlation. Based on their environmental attitudes, most respondents did not favor cutting trees, squatting, mining, forest fires, river drilling, quarrying, hunting, and using inorganic fertilizers. Based on the study's conclusions, it was recommended that the school's environmental programs, campaigns, and community extension services can help the learners maintain a healthy environment by implementing the existing environmental laws.

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Introduction

The environment has given everything to living organisms. There is no longer any room for denial regarding the rapid depletion of the planet's natural resources and the rapid destruction of its ecosystem, which presents the greatest dangers to both people and animals (Marpa & Juele, 2016). Environmental issues have been recognized as one of today's most significant problems (Degirmenci, 2013). Pollutants generated through numerous anthropogenic activities and industrialization may be released into the air, water, or soil and could harm biodiversity, ecosystems, and the well-being of individuals. The environment's health deteriorates faster because humans ignore it (Adlaon, 2021).

Environmental education can help to reduce and avoid current and future environmental problems (Sindhu & Singh, 2014). These attempts to educate environmentally aware individuals who are aware of environmental problems and can contribute to their solutions (Ozturk & Ozturk, 2015). It is vital and suitable for the learners to have a value of awareness, attitudes, and practices towards the environment. To preserve students' ecological awareness at a high level, the school could continue information distribution activities about environmental ideas, the state of the environment, ecological difficulties, and problems (Rogayan & Nebrida, 2019). As the basis and beginning of literacy, one must be conscious of the environment around them (Burchett, 2015).

Through a comprehensive legal and regulatory framework, the Philippine Government has tried to impose environmental protection and natural resource management, which will aid in addressing current environmental concerns. Republic Act 9512 also known as the "National Environmental Awareness and Education Act of 2008" was approved on December 12, 2008. This act will be the main door for the other departments and institutions to create policies in their respective areas. The Department of Education has extended its goal toward the learners and teachers through DO 52, S. 2011 - Strengthening Environmental Education in Public and Private

Schools in which to support government efforts to combat climate change as the Department of Education has implemented measures and policies to promote environmental education in both public and private schools. It highlights all science subjects to intensify the lessons about the environment and should be integrated into learning areas. Students' participation in environmental initiatives and campaigns will be encouraged, and a sense of responsibility for preserving and protecting the environment will be instilled in them. Therefore, school administrators, officials, and teachers are now requested to incorporate environmental concerns and issues into their instructional material (Department of Education, 2011). It is now in the hands of the school especially the teachers, which they can serve as a model for environmentally friendly practices by decreasing its carbon emissions using sources of renewable energy, waste disposal, recycling, and other methods that are environmentally friendly so that the learners not just also apply it at school but also to the community.

The core messages or seven environmental themes were presented with the full list of environmental education's guiding principles recognized by the Department of Environment and Natural Resources-Environment Management Bureau (DENR-EMB) (Hinojosa, 1996; Punzalan, 2020). These are the following list of seven environmental themes: 1) Interdependence. Everything is related to everything; 2) Change. Everything changes. Some changes enhance the natural state of the environment, others degrade it; 3) Diversity and stability. Diversity is essential. It promotes stability; 4) Finiteness of Resources. Most of the earth's resources are finite. Therefore, they must be used prudently and wisely; 5) Materials cycle. Everything must go somewhere and end somewhere; 6) Balance of nature. Nature has laws and processes to maintain it.; and 7) Stewardship. The natural world includes people. They are stewards of the planet rather than their masters. The environmental protection agency's themes served as the foundation for research issues resolved by a range of experts in the field (Punzalan, 2020).

Taking good care of the environment is just one-way of preserving the future for the next generations. If there are no actions taken, the environment would suffer destruction. Humans as rational beings should act in terms of preventing such activities that cause harm to the environment. Preservation and protection of the environment should not just be limited to instilling it in the people, especially the young minds, but also it needs to be practiced and must become a habit to achieve a healthy environment. To solve ecological disasters, everyone must work together, not just policymakers, scientists, and environmentalists (Bautista, 2019).

Students are given special attention since they are considered the nation's future, and schools are expected to develop their potential as advocates for a sustainable environment (Ahmad *et al.*, 2015). This study aimed to investigate the environmental awareness, practices, and attitudes of chosen private senior high school, particularly grades 11 and 12 in Surigao City, Philippines, during the Academic Year 2022-2023. STEM students were the participants in this study. Specifically, it aimed to achieve the following: (1) demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, grade level, and source of environmental information through mass media; (2) assess the level of environmental awareness of the respondents in terms of seven environmental themes; (3) determine the environmental practices of the respondents in terms of seven environmental themes; (4) evaluate the respondents' attitudes toward various environmental issues concerning the seven environmental themes; (5) ascertain a significant relationship between the level of environmental awareness and practices of the selected private senior high school in Surigao City, Philippines.

Material and methods

Research Design

This quantitative research study employed a correlational descriptive method to investigate the relationship between senior high school students' environmental awareness and practices. A correlational research design is a non-experimental

research approach in which two variables are measured and their association is assessed with little or no purpose of controlling for other variables (Chiang *et al.*, 2015).

Participants

The participants of this research were the Grade 11 and 12 STEM students at a respective private senior high school in Surigao City, Philippines. The respondents were selected through purposive-convenience sampling, to assess their awareness of the environment, attitude, and practices. STEM students were chosen to be the respondents of this study since they have more exposure to science subjects than the other academic strands in senior high school. 223 respondents willingly participated when the study was conducted.

Instrumentation

The study used the adopted survey questionnaire from Pardo (2012). These consisted of three parts: Environmental Awareness Test, Environmental Practices Test, and Environmental Attitude. These include items on environmental awareness, attitude, and practices tests based on the seven environmental themes, which were as follows: stewardship, finiteness of resources, diversity, and stability, change, material cycle, balance nature, and interdependence.

Data Collection Procedure

Survey questionnaires were administered after the school administration's approval and the respondents' consent. The respondents were given an adequate opportunity to respond to all the statements in the instrument and they willingly participated during the data gathering. Before taking the survey, all participants were informed about the study's objectives. Respondents who were absent were not included in the data gathering and the students who did not participate were hereby not forced to.

Data Analysis

The statistical application used is SPSS Statistics 27 to analyze frequency, mean, percentage distribution and correlation analysis from the data gathered.

Result and discussion

This section contains the results and the discussion of the study "Environmental Awareness, Attitudes, and Practices of The Selected Private Senior High School in Surigao City, Philippines."

Respondents' Demographic Profile

Table 1 displays the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, grade level, and source of environmental information through mass media exposure.

Among the participants, 119 (53.4%) students were from grade 11, and 104 (46.6%) were from grade 12. When it comes to age, 86 (38.6%) respondents were 17 years old, 76 (34.1%) respondents were 18 years old, 44 (19.7%) respondents were 16 years old, 14 (6.3%) respondents were 19 years old, 2 (0.9%) respondents were 15 years old, and 1 (0.4%) respondent is 20 years old. In terms of their sex profile, 132 (59.2%) respondents were female, and 91 (40.8%) respondents were male.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents.

Profile	Frequency	Percent
Age		
15	2	0.9%
16	44	19.7%
17	86	38.6%
18	76	34.1%
19	14	6.3%
20	1	0.4%
Sex		
Female	132	59.2%
Male	91	40.8%
Grade Level		
11	119	53.4%
12	104	46.6%
Source of Environmental Information Through Mass Media Exposure		
Newspapers and other Periodicals	18	8.1%
Internet	182	81.6%
Radio & Television	23	10.3%
TOTAL	223	100%

Based on their source of environmental information through mass media exposure, 182 (81.6%) respondents were using the internet as a means of getting information about the environment, 23 (10.3%) respondents have radio and television as

their way of learning about the factual status and events about the environment, and 18 (8.1%) respondents still preferred to use newspapers and other periodicals as their source of information about the environment.

Environmental Awareness and Practices Tests

Table 2 shows respondents' total item mean rating on their environmental awareness level and practices throughout the seven environmental themes. Table 3 was the descriptive interpretation of the mean.

The first environmental theme is about stewardship that humans supervise and show responsibility for protecting the environment. The results showed that the respondents have a "very high" level of environmental awareness with a mean rating of 4.36 and "strongly agree" that they should treat animals with care and take good care of the plants since they are the stewards of the Earth. The responsible use and preservation of the environment through sustainable approaches tend to promote ecosystem resilience and well-being for humans (Chapin *et al.*, 2010).

In terms of the practices, it resulted in "very good" with its mean rating of 4.33 since they minimize the use of pesticides as the attraction between soil particles and pesticides in sorption systems, which is influenced by soil organic matter and soil texture, causes pesticides to remain in the soil for a long time and harm the ecosystem (Qin *et al.*, 2014).

They also avoid buying materials that are made up of some body parts of the animals. Most of the leather and fur products are produced in factories, where the animals are kept in filthy, cramped cages and then ruthlessly killed. Alligators whose skin is used to make handbags, in particular, are raised in a single tank, locked, and shot or otherwise murdered at the age of three. As a result, three to four alligators are slaughtered to make one handbag (Hoskins, 2014).

The second environmental theme is about the finiteness of the resources depicting the abundance of the natural resources at risk.

The level of environmental awareness resulted in respondents' responses to "very high" garnering a mean rating of 4.42 as they "strongly agree" that planting can help with more production of plants. Plantations can provide essential ecosystem services such as carbon capture, storage, biodiversity promotion, and economic benefits (Paquette & Messier, 2010). They do not engage in any illegal fishing as it destroys the population of marine organisms, and cutting trees should be minimized. The function of local ecosystems and the way of life of coastal communities can be significantly impacted by

the illegal harvest of marine species within the boundaries of exclusive economic zones (Aceves-Bueno *et al.*, 2021). The environmental practices gained a result of "very good" with a rating of 4.56 as students plant trees in replacement to the tree that has been cut off and consumed and contributes by not participating in any illegal activities, whether in the land or water. Tree planting is a tool for achieving certain goals, and it should be evaluated as part of a multidisciplinary decision-making process that thoroughly weighs consequences and unanticipated events (Chazdon & Brancalion, 2019).

Table 2. Respondents' total item mean ratings on their level of environmental awareness and environmental practices throughout the seven environmental themes, N= 223.

Seven Environmental Themes	Level of Environmental Awareness		Environmental Practices	
	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Man: God's Caretaker (Stewardship)	4.36	VH	4.33	VG
2. The Earth - For the Future Generations Too (Finiteness of Resources)	4.42	VH	4.56	VG
3. The Earth is Rich with Natural Resources (Diversity and Stability)	4.20	H	4.40	VG
4. Most of the Earth's Resources are now Depleting (Change)	4.17	H	4.12	G
5. Everything Must Go Somewhere and Ends Somewhere (Materials Cycle)	4.23	VH	4.32	VG
6. The World is Very Beautiful-It's God's Gift to Us (Balance of Nature)	4.41	VH	4.40	VG
7. The earth is fragile and dying. I must have to take care of it, heal and save it the best way I can. I can do a lot (Interdependence)	4.40	VH	4.36	VG
A. At Home	4.42	VH	4.42	VG
B. In Public Places	4.42	VH	4.34	VG
C. In the Community Where I Belong	4.37	VH	4.32	VG
OVERALL MEAN	4.31	VH	4.36	VG

Table 3. Descriptive Interpretation for the Level of Environmental Awareness and Environmental Practices.

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent: Awareness		Descriptive Equivalent: Practices	
	Item Definition	Interpretation	Item Definition	Interpretation
4.21-5.0	Strongly Agree	Very High (VH)	Very Often	Very Good (VG)
3.41-4.20	Agree	High (H)	Often	Good (G)
2.61-3.40	Fairly Agree	Average (A)	Sometimes	Poor (P)
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low (L)	Seldom	Very Poor (VP)
1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low (VL)	Never	Needs Improvement (NI)

Diversity and stability are the third environmental theme portraying that greater diversity will lead to greater stability. The level of environmental awareness has resulted to "high" with its mean rating of 4,20 since they "agree" that earth's natural resources will not last due to excessive usage, and the possible extinction of some species due to over-exploitation and hunting caused by humanity. Due

primarily to habitat loss and overhunting, biodiversity worldwide is declining (Maxwell *et al.*,2016). Their environmental practices resulted in "very good" with a rating of 4.40 as they did not participate in capturing any endangered animals to maintain ecological balance and they would not want to have many children as they desire since overpopulation will cause scarcity of resources or it will exceed the

carrying capacity. Overpopulation's most important consequences are deforestation, impact on welfare, climate change, the decline in bio-capacity, urban sprawl, food security, increased energy use, and impact on marine ecosystems. To preserve the sustainability of natural resources for future generations, it is necessary to take proactive measures against the negative impacts of overpopulation on both a national and global level (Uniyal *et al.*, 2020).

The fourth environmental theme is about change, representing the environmental disturbance from artificial and natural activities. The respondents gained a result of "high" with a rating of 4.17 in terms of awareness. They "agree" that potable water is essential to living organisms and production. Infiltration of contaminants into water pipes, leaching, the byproducts of disinfection, chemical or microbiological permeation, and pollution are only a few examples of the physical, operational, and environmental variables that could threaten potable water (Dawood *et al.*, 2020). The usage of detergents affects the quality of the soil. Detergent compounds can enter soil and water from various sources, altering the flora and fauna and impacting ecosystems directly and indirectly (Mousavi & Khodadoost, 2019). Respondents' response on environmental practices resulted in "good" with a rating of 4.12. They prefer to walk short distances rather than ride a motorbike or tricycle to save gas. Walking saves money on petrol and vehicle maintenance in the long run, while driving less minimizes one's carbon footprint.

The materials cycle is the fifth environmental theme which signifies the flow of matter from the abiotic to the biotic world and vice versa. The respondents have a result of "very high" with a mean rating of 4.23 in terms of their level of environmental awareness. They "strongly agree" that recycling can help reduce waste and can be used to earn money from it. As a result, more plastic is being consumed due to increased population, contributing to a rise in plastic trash. Effective steps must be implemented to lessen the effects of plastic waste, such as reducing, reusing, and recycling (3Rs) or energy recovery from plastic waste

(Wichai-utcha & Chavalparit, 2018). Inorganic fertilizers must be limited to prevent soil degradation, especially in farming. The environmental practices results from the respondents earned a result of "very good" at a mean rating of 4.32. They have been practicing not throwing garbage, especially plastics at the window and when traveling to prevent waste problems on the streets and water bodies. Plastic can pollute land, streams, and oceans due to its failure to biodegrade and the risks it causes to the soil. Plastic pollution has already caused the demise of numerous marine and terrestrial animals. It also emits toxic gases when heated or exposed. The landfilling up and clogging drainage systems cause floods and erosion (Kehinde *et al.*, 2020).

As the sixth environmental theme, the balance of nature shows the interaction between biotic and abiotic components in equilibrium making them interdependent. The imbalance can lead to a serious problem in the whole ecosystem. The result showed "very high" with a rating of 4.41 from the respondents regarding their level of environmental awareness as they "strongly agree" that fresh air can give living organisms good health. Along with clearing the lungs, breathing in the fresh air can help enhance digestion, and lower blood pressure, mood, and energy levels (Grossman, 2022). The open fields like mountains and hills are a work of art by God and should be cared for. Recreational activities are appropriate on clean rivers and beaches. People volunteer to collect beach trash to make the beach a more enjoyable and secure environment for everyone. By preventing trash from harming marine life or being damaging enough to disrupt the aquatic life cycle, beach cleanup supports the coastal and ocean ecosystems (Dodds, 2019). With the environmental practices, "very good" is the result with a rating of 4.40. The students practice "CLAYGO" before leaving the place to maintain a healthy and clean environment. Clean as you go is a cleaning practice that aids in improving hygiene, health, and safety. Cleaning is done continuously throughout the working day with this strategy, becoming a part of the routine. This strategy ensures that all surfaces, equipment, and facilities are always

clean, sterile, and clutter-free (Crawley, 2023). To also minimize the consumption of cosmetics to lessen its production that causes the contribution of microplastics in the environment. It sends numerous microplastics down the drain with cosmetics while using a product containing micro-beads. They attract poisons and are subsequently consumed by fish and humans (Okafor, 2021).

Interdependence is the seventh environmental theme. The species in the ecosystem depend on one another making them have mutual dependence between biotic and abiotic factors. This area has been divided into At Home, In Public Places, and In the Community Where I Belong. In terms of the respondents' level of environmental awareness at home, the results showed "very high" at a rating of 4.42 and they "strongly agree" that proper sanitation can contribute to healthy living, cleaning the house always as wastes can attract rodents or any organisms that can bring disease, and conserve energy when a certain appliance is not needed to be used. Cleanliness of the environment can help prevent the spread of infectious diseases (Vargova, *et al.*, 2020). With environmental practices, respondents have a result of "very good" with a rating of 4.42 in which they practice proper disposal of waste at home, conserving energy by switching off the lights and opening the windows in the morning, planting trees at home to counteract the effects of pollution, and have proper hygiene by using the comfort room as a place for excreting the wastes from the body. In public places, the results showed "very high" at a mean rating of 4.42 as students "strongly agree" that smoke-belching causes harm to the environment and can cause disease, and non-biodegradable materials are the primary source of pollution on land. Their environmental practices showed "very good" with a rating of 4.34 in which they practice covering their nose when they happen to pass a vehicle and bringing eco-bags when going to the supermarket to reduce the use of plastic materials that causes harm to the environment. In contrast to many other contemporary materials, plastic not only takes expensive resources to make, such as petroleum and natural gas but also significantly pollutes the

environment because it cannot decompose. Utilizing eco-friendly bags contributes to the reduction of non-biodegradable wastes like plastic (Evans, 2019). For the last part of interdependence the in the community where I belong, the result of the respondents' responses showed "very high" with a rating of 4.37 in which they "strongly agree" that a clean and green program from the environment can help promote and maintain a healthy community. Improving forest operations is the most suitable and economical way to reduce CO₂ emissions (Arshad *et al.*, 2020). Deforestation can cause soil erosion and floods, affecting living organisms and their livelihood, and for sanitary purposes, each home must have a toilet. For environmental practices, "very good" at a mean of 4.32 because of the students' responses. They bury the dead in a respective area, and it does not limit also to the human, it includes pets who passed away also. They support the usage of septic tanks if there is a piggery so that the waste from the pigs will not cause a disease to the community, and to fill the stagnant waters with soil or throw the water regularly to prevent diseases carried by mosquitoes.

Increased environmental pollution, climate change, resource depletion, and other unfavorable effects on the environment and society are only a few of the negative effects of globalization. Guaranteeing the rights of people to a clean environment is challenging because of these processes, and enforcing these rights necessitates competent solutions (Perkumiené *et al.*, 2020). The overall mean showed "very high" in terms of their level of environmental awareness, especially with the environmental issues that society faces today. The environmental practices earned "very good" as they practice what is best for the environment by simply avoiding the practices that can cause harm to the environment.

Respondents attitudes towards the issues on the environment themes

Respondents were asked to express their feelings, ideas, opinions, and attitudes concerning the environmental issues presented below. This was done to elicit responses that reflected the respondents'

attitudes on the many current environmental problems. Table 4 shows the results of the analysis.

The following are answers from persons who discussed their opinions on the matter

Most respondents were "Not In Favor" of Cutting of Trees with a percentage of 91.9% and only 8.1% were "In Favor". They stated, "Cutting trees can affect the environment's temperature". Others stated that "Cutting of trees contributes to more environmental problems like flooding, soil erosion, and destruction of the habitat of animals." Most of them stated that trees should be given relevance and importance in the community as it helps the organisms to get oxygen especially, they are autotroph.

Table 4. Respondents' Attitudes Towards the Issues on the Environmental Themes through Frequency, Percentage Distribution, and Overall Average.

Environmental Issues	Favor		Not In Favor	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Cutting of Trees	18	8.1%	205	91.9%
Road Widening	135	60.5%	88	39.5%
Squatting	35	15.7%	188	84.3%
Mining	49	22%	174	78%
Forest Fires	0	0%	223	100%
River Drilling	21	9.4%	202	90.6%
Quarrying	26	11.7%	197	88.3%
Hunting	34	15.2%	189	84.8%
Use of Inorganic Fertilizer	35	15.7%	188	84.3%
Industrialization	101	45.3%	122	54.7%
OVERALL AVERAGE	45	20	178	80

More students were "In Favor" of road widening with a percentage of 60.5% compared to those who were "Not In Favor" wherein it has only 39.5%. To those who were in favor, most of them agreed that "Road widening can prevent traffic"; "It makes the road larger making more vehicles can accessibly pass easily". However, to those who are not in favor, they reasoned out that, "Road widening means more cutting of trees, and simply creates another environmental problem."; "More houses and livelihoods will be affected."; "The natural resources can be destroyed in just a snap through road widening."

Squatting garnered an 84.3% result of "Not In Favor" and 15.7% to those who were "In Favor". Students stated that "Squatting causes serious problems in

terms of health and sanitation."; Most of them do not use the toilet since they occupied a lot not intended for them, making it hard to plan for a proper sewage system."; Some of them will leave their wastes in which it attracts pests.", as these were the reasons of those students who are "Not In Favor". In contrast, "Unused land should be used by some random people since no one has used it."; "Squatting can make a home for a homeless person, and they can maintain a clean environment as long as they clean the area."

The respondents are "Not In Favor" of mining with a percentage of 78% and 22% to those who are "In Favor". To those who are in favor of mining, "It gives us important minerals and ores that can be used in our daily lives."; "It helps the modernization of the gadgets and other stuff."; "All we see anywhere came from the mining industry." The respondents who are not in favor, "Mining damages the mountains." as some of them stated. "It pollutes the environment and cuts off more trees."

All respondents are "Not In Favor" of forest fires. They stated, "It just not damages the trees but also the habitat of the animals."; "It damages Mother Earth and kills wild animals."; "It affects the livelihood of the people."; "It decreases the populations of the animals in the area since there is no food and shelter.'

There were 90.6% who were "Not In Favor" of river drilling and only 9.4% were "In Favor". These are the following statements of the respondents who were not in favor: "River drilling disrupts fishes in the water"; "It disturbs land and aquatic organisms.". These were the reasons the respondent favored, "It is used to obtain detailed information below the surface of the water."

Quarrying has 88.3% of respondents who were "Not In Favor" and 11.7% who were "In Favor". "This provides materials for the people in the industry." as those who were in favor stated. "It dangers the photosynthesis of the plants."; "It disfigures the environment."; "It can cause deforestation." as the respondents who were not in favor stated.

In hunting, 84.8% of respondents were “Not In Favor” and 15.2% to those who were “In Favor”. The reasons of the students who were not in favor of hunting: “This will cause the extinction of wildlife.” most of them stated. To those who were in favor, “Hunting gives food to the other organisms.”; “It can benefit others and eliminate the weak ones in the group.” stated.

There were 84.3% who were “Not In Favor” and 15.7% were “In Favor” in terms of inorganic fertilizers. Most of the respondents who were not in favor stated, “Using inorganic fertilizer can pollute the groundwater.”; “It has and can damage plants.”; “It changes the pH of the soil.”; Releases greenhouse gases to the atmosphere.” To those who were in favor, “It makes a rapid growth for plants and can be put in the market easily.”; “This is easy to use and gives effect to the plants immediately.”

For industrialization, 54.7% of respondents were “Not In Favor” and 45.3% to those who were “In Favor”. Some say, “Industrialization makes living productive.”; “It improves medical care.”. Others stated that “It deteriorates the quality of air, and water, and produces contaminants.”; “Affects the life expectancy.”; “It causes exploitation and extinction of species.”

This indicates that the students have a pleasant and positive attitude toward the environment, as evidenced by their sentiments, ideas, and opinions about the issues addressed in this study and their extremely high level of awareness and positive practices regarding the seven environmental themes. According to their environmental attitudes, 88% of respondents opposed cutting trees, squatting, mining, forest fires, river drilling, quarrying, hunting, and using inorganic fertilizers.

The Significant Relationship Between the Awareness and Practice of The Respondents Toward the Seven Environmental Themes

Table 5 presents the significant relationship between environmental awareness and practices toward the seven environmental themes by correlation.

The researchers used a correlation analysis to determine whether there is a significant relationship between the level of environmental awareness and the practices among senior high school students at a selected private senior high school. As shown in Table 5, the analysis revealed a Pearson Correlation coefficient of 0.802, indicating a “positive correlation” between the two variables. This means that the level of awareness of the senior high school students is significantly related to their practice along the seven environmental themes namely: stewardship, finiteness of resources, diversity and stability, change, material cycle, balance nature, and interdependence.

Table 5. The significant relationship between the awareness and practice of the respondents toward the seven environmental themes.

Correlations			
		Awareness	Practices
Awareness	Pearson Correlation	1	.802**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<0.001
	N	223	223
Practices	Pearson Correlation	.802**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	
	N	223	223

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

A study entitled, Environmental Awareness, Practices, and Attitudes of UNP Students (Pardo, 2012), entails the level of awareness and practices of the respondents with the seven environmental themes were found to be significantly correlated using correlation analysis. The student's awareness and practices toward the environment give significance to a healthier and better future for the environment. There needs to be more than just awareness of such environmental issues to battle for a cleaner environment as it should be practiced anywhere else with guiding principles of the environment in terms of the seven environmental themes.

The study conducted by Punzalan (2020) entitled Evaluating the Environmental Awareness and Practices of Senior High School Students: Basis for Environmental Education Program revealed that, the extent of the environmental practice of senior high school students is significantly and substantially related to their level of awareness of the environment.

It also pointed out that student's current understanding of issues related to the environment meets the acceptable level of practice, even though one theme, "change," received a lower level than the other three themes. It has been demonstrated that what the students know about environmental issues may be transformed into actions that allow them to resolve these problems using their existing knowledge.

Conclusion

This study aimed to assess environmental awareness, attitudes, and practices among students in a selected private senior high school in Surigao City, Philippines, during the academic year 2022-2023. The researchers used an established survey questionnaire separated into three categories: environmental practices, attitudes, and awareness. The demographic profile of the respondents was gathered, including grade level, age, and sex. The research also looked at the students' sources of environmental information, with the majority depending on the Internet.

Despite society's environmental concerns, the findings showed that students had a "very high" level of environmental awareness. Their environmental practices were assessed as "very good," indicating they avoided detrimental behaviors. The students exhibited a positive attitude toward the environment, with most opposing activities such as quarrying, hunting, squatting, mining, forest fires, and using inorganic fertilizers.

In addition, the study discovered a significant relationship between the student's level of environmental awareness and environmental practices. The Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.802 suggested a strong positive correlation between these factors. This implies that students more aware of environmental issues were more inclined to engage in ecologically friendly practices.

The study's findings show students' favorable environmental awareness, attitudes, and practices at the selected private senior high school. The findings highlight the necessity of increasing environmental education and encouraging environmentally friendly

student behaviors to contribute to a healthy environment. It highlighted that the quality of the earth's environment depends on students because they are the future leaders and the most qualified individuals to defend the environment (Magulod, 2018).

Recommendation(S):

With such education, students can learn about the benefits of a healthy environment and the negative consequences of environmental deterioration. Schools are encouraged to give environmental education and inspire students to consistently safeguard the environment. This can be accomplished by strictly enforcing environmental rules and cultivating a culture of environmental responsibility and sustainability among students.

Students can actively participate in environmental education programs and campaigns to increase awareness and comprehension of environmental issues. They can pursue solutions to urgent environmental issues. They can also research, make recommendations, and create conservation measures or methods to deal with environmental issues. It will be best to support eco-friendly goods and services, reduce their carbon footprint, practice resource conservation, recycle, and urge others to follow suit.

Students develop a sense of responsibility and cleanliness by simply picking up trash, resulting in a clean and pleasant learning environment. Students can contribute directly to environmental conservation efforts by participating in activities outside of school such as tree planting, coastal clean-ups, and campaigning for a clean and green environment campaign. Recycling campaigns to limit the usage of non-biodegradable materials support sustainable behaviors as well. Through these acts, creating a cleaner and healthier environment that will benefit current and future generations is possible.

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